

"A PROFESSIONAL LIMITED LIABILITY COMPANY"

"Fahl & Donaldson is a Houston law firm with extensive litigation experience in matters of negligence and tort liability, insurance defense, trucking accident defense and construction law. Our Houston civil litigation attorneys also provide guidance and representation in matters of estate planning and probate. If you need trial-ready representation to protect your company from liability, our Houston business litigation lawyers can help. Let our attorneys' 100 years of combined experience work for you. Our liability defense law firm is based in Houston, but we represent clients throughout Texas."

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